

VeRAPAK: Distributed Counterexample Generation via Iterative Neural Network Verification and Falsification

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Abstract—Formally verifying and improving the adversarial robustness of deep neural networks is extremely challenging. Existing verification tools face a fundamental tradeoff: abstract interpretation scales to large networks but sacrifices completeness, while SMT solvers are complete but do not scale; and both frequently return UNKNOWN on large or complex input regions, leaving users with no actionable result. Improving the adversarial robustness of deep neural networks requires retraining on counterexamples representative of the full range of unsafe behavior, but generating such counterexamples is computationally expensive. We present VERAPAK (*Verification for Robust neural networks through Abstraction, Partitioning and Attack methods*), an adversarial robustness verification framework that resolves both problems through iterative refinement combined with targeted falsification. Rather than verifying a region in a single pass, VERAPAK progressively subdivides uncertain regions into smaller subproblems where verification eventually succeeds; this enables incomplete tools to achieve practical completeness where they would otherwise fail. At each subdivision, VERAPAK also searches for counterexamples using RFGSM: a novel, randomized variant of the Fast Gradient Sign Method. Unlike FGSM, which generates counterexamples along a single gradient direction, RFGSM spans an m -dimensional hyperplane. Combined with the iterative subdivision, this produces a *covering set* of adversarial examples distributed approximately uniformly across the unsafe subregion. Covering sets are experimentally shown to yield improved adversarial retraining outcomes compared to standard single-point gradient methods and unpartitioned baselines. Beyond these contributions, VERAPAK’s engines are fully interchangeable, making the framework compatible with any existing or future verification, falsification, or partitioning strategy.

Index Terms—Neural network verification, Adversarial robustness, Adversarial examples, Iterative refinement, Abstract interpretation, Falsification, Anytime algorithms, Adversarial retraining, Covering sets

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the popularity and complexity of *Deep Neural Networks* (DNNs) has increased dramatically. As generative AI has grabbed the public eye, DNNs have also been put to use—often in systems of far greater consequence. It is therefore increasingly necessary to provide provable guarantees of

success and avoidance of failure: failures that could result in destruction of property or loss of life in safety-critical systems, such as the perception modules of autonomous vehicles or collision avoidance systems in unmanned aircraft. As long as humans have the time and attention to intercept, risks are minimized. However, as trust in these systems increases, we are beginning to see usage in situations where bad outputs might crash a car or a plane, meltdown a nuclear reactor, or send munitions to the wrong destination.

We present VERAPAK (*Verification for Robust neural networks through Abstraction, Partitioning and Attack methods*), an algorithmic framework for the adversarial robustness verification of DNNs.

Neural network verification is fundamentally challenging: proving that a network behaves correctly over an entire input region requires reasoning about numerous complex transformations, often with increasingly large input spaces. Some tools use abstract interpretation to over-approximate network behavior, thus trading completeness for scalability; others use SMT solvers for exact verification, trading scalability for completeness. This is the key tradeoff that most solvers try to fine-tune: scalability versus completeness. VERAPAK is built to help answer this problem, but also tackles another problem with these tools: when applied to large regions or complex networks, tools often return UNKNOWN or POSSIBLY_UNSAFE, leaving users with no actionable information. This is sometimes as a result of timeout, uncertainty due to approximation, or that the region does in fact contain both safe and unsafe points.

VERAPAK addresses this limitation through **iterative refinement**: rather than attempting to verify a region in a single pass, it progressively subdivides uncertain regions into smaller, more tractable subproblems. By subdividing, we reduce the volume of the region and thereby reduce both the complexity of computing the reachable space and the odds of containing both safe and unsafe points. When used alongside a verification tool that prioritizes speed, this has a few key advantages:

- 1) If the verifier could determine safety, then no complexity

is added.

- 2) When approximations are too great and the verifier could not determine safety, then it eventually will.¹
- 3) VERAPAK will create a complete map of safety versus unsafety in the region, yielding the exact decision boundaries.

Beyond simply *determining* safety, one of the fundamental issues in the verification space is that of *improving* safety. However, improving the model generally requires retraining with a large number of counterexamples representative of the full range of unsafe behavior. Testing points likely to be unsafe — such as those generated by gradient-guided methods like FGSM [1] — finds counterexamples quickly, but they are not representative of the whole region. Testing points uniformly throughout the region provides broader coverage but rarely finds enough counterexamples in practice, since unsafe points may occupy only a small fraction of the region. The optimal solution would be *targeted but diverse*: with a high hit rate and broad spatial coverage.

VERAPAK also has an answer to this problem: adding a **falsification step** to every iteration which uses targeted falsification methods from a diverse number of points. Because the regions get iteratively smaller, the longer that VERAPAK runs, the better the coverage of its counterexamples, since falsification operates on progressively smaller and more targeted subregions. When using the novel randomized variant of FGSM (RFGSM) proposed in this paper, this effect is further strengthened. We also eliminate a large amount of wasted computation by pruning subregions that are fully safe or fully unsafe, and beyond this, we can terminate early when simply trying to prove or disprove safety.

Our contributions can be summarized as follows. We (i) present VERAPAK (*Verification for Robust neural networks through Abstraction, Partitioning and Attack methods*), a modular framework for adversarial robustness verification of DNNs that combines iterative refinement with targeted falsification; (ii) propose RFGSM, a randomized variant of FGSM that improves spatial coverage of generated counterexamples; (iii) demonstrate practical completeness on regions where they would otherwise return UNKNOWN, evaluated against ERAN as a representative incomplete verifier; and (iv) show that the covering counterexample sets produced by VERAPAK yield measurably improved adversarial retraining outcomes compared to single-pass falsification methods.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II surveys existing adversarial attack algorithms and neural network verification tools. Section III establishes the notation and foundational definitions used throughout. The VERAPAK framework — its verification, falsification, and partitioning engines and their formal properties — is described in full in Section IV. Experimental results are presented in Section V, and Section VI concludes.

¹See Section IV-C for more on termination.

II. RELATED WORK

Adversarial vulnerability — the susceptibility of DNNs to inputs that are nearly indistinguishable from safe ones yet cause large, unexpected output changes — is well documented across architectures and datasets [1]–[3]. Linear behavior in high-dimensional spaces [1] and feature embedding instability [4] have both been identified as causes. Critically, adversarial examples transfer across architectures and training sets [1], [5], survive real-world transformations such as physically modified road signs [6], and enable black-box attacks against unknown models [7]. These findings demonstrate that adversarial examples are abundant, transferable, and robust under transformation. However, prior work primarily focuses on finding individual counterexamples, rather than characterizing the structure of the unsafe region itself. This leaves open the question of whether generating spatially distributed counterexamples can provide additional benefits — a question VERAPAK is designed to explore.

A. Adversarial Attack Algorithms

The primary limitation of standard attack algorithms is their narrow spatial coverage. FGSM [1] prioritizes speed, using a single gradient step to find counterexamples that inevitably cluster along a single line. While JSMA [8] uses Jacobian-guided iterations for targeted misclassification, it follows local gradients too closely to generate the diverse covering sets required for robust region characterization. RFGSM (Section IV-B) extends FGSM by replacing low-impact dimension with randomness, extending the cluster from a line to an m -dimensional hyperplane.

R+FGSM [9] prepends a random step to escape sharp local gradient curvature.

B. Neural Network Verification

Formal verification prioritizes completeness over scalability. *Exact* methods like Marabou 2.0 [10] and Reluplex [11] use SMT-based case-splitting to manage ReLU activations. Other approaches leverage MIP-based solvers [12] or Z3-encoded activations [13] to produce tight bounds. However, these methods frequently run out of memory or time when applied to large input regions or complex architectures.

Approximate methods, such as ERAN [14] and NNV [15], favor scalability by propagating abstract polytopes or ImageStars through network layers. While efficient, their sound-but-incomplete nature leads to over-approximation, which significantly weakens most of its claims of unsafety to mean simply UNKNOWN.

State-of-the-art verifiers like α, β -CROWN [16] combine bound propagation with branch-and-bound search, yet their primary objective remains single-instance certification. Even verification-style attacks like BaB-Attack [17] focus on finding the *strongest* individual counterexample rather than constructing a distributed set. **VERAPAK complements these tools by using their engines to map regions and generate covering counterexamples — capabilities no standalone verifier provides.**

Tool	Approach	Complete?	Anytime?	Cov. CEs?
Reluplex/Marabou	SMT	✓	×	×
ERAN/PRIMA	Abs. interp.	×	×	×
α - β -CROWN	BaB + prop.	✓	×	×
NNV	Reachability	Optional	×	×
FGSM / PGD	Attack only	×	—	×
VERAPAK	Hybrid	Best-eff.	✓	✓

TABLE I: Comparison of key approaches. “Complete” = can formally prove safety. “Anytime” = valid partial results under early termination. “Cov. CEs” = covering counterexample generation.

C. Iterative Refinement, Retraining, and VERAPAK

Region subdivision is used internally by Marabou [10], α , β -CROWN [16], and NNV [15], but they do not expose these subregions to the user or run falsification at intermediate levels. Consequently, users receive a binary classification rather than a map of safe and unsafe space. VERAPAK treats subdivision as an explicit, engine-agnostic mechanism for systematic exploration of the input region and the construction of covering sets of counterexamples.

Adversarial retraining has been shown to improve robustness [1], [5], [18], but examples generated along a single gradient direction may fail to capture the diversity of the local adversarial region, potentially limiting their effectiveness for robust retraining [1], [9]. Zhang et al. [19] show that adversarial retraining tends to only be effective on points that are close to the retraining points in some embedding space.

Just as Madry et al. start PGD multiple times throughout the region to better explore the loss landscape [18], VERAPAK creates counterexamples at every iteration, spreading them throughout the entire search space. Prior work has found that using selection criteria for counterexamples can improve retraining results [20], proving that the quality of counterexamples does in fact matter. No existing tool generates spatially distributed sets of counterexamples as a byproduct of verification. While DI²-FGSM has shown that increased input diversity improves the *transferability* of adversarial examples, VERAPAK’s covering sets are shown in Section V to yield improved *robustness after retraining* compared to other methods.

While prior work has explored adversarial diversity for transferability, selection strategies for retraining, and robustness under stronger attacks, no work has jointly studied verification-driven partitioning, covering counterexample generation, and their downstream impact on retraining.

III. PRELIMINARIES

This section establishes the notation and foundational concepts used throughout the paper. We model a neural network as a continuous, piecewise-differentiable function $NN : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, where n and m denote the dimensionality of the input and output spaces \mathbb{R}^n and \mathbb{R}^m , respectively. We refer to a specific

value in the input or output space as $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ or $\vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, respectively.

A subset of the input space can be specified using **regions**. For the purpose of this paper, a region $\mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{R}$ is defined by n closed intervals (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n) forming an axis-aligned box, such that $\vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} \implies \forall j \in 1..n : \vec{x}_j \in i_j$.

Definition 1 (Safety Predicate). A function $S : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \{\text{SAFE}, \text{UNSAFE}\}$ whose result represents whether a given output satisfies a desired property. This highly general definition allows the safety predicate to encode any notion of robustness.

A typical use of this predicate captures **local adversarial robustness**: the property that for a known safe point $\vec{s} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and a surrounding region $\mathbf{R}_{\vec{s}}$, all points $\vec{x} \in \mathbf{R}_{\vec{s}}$ produce a semantically equal output as \vec{s} . Let $\vec{y}_1 \cong \vec{y}_2$ denote *semantic equality*: that two outputs can reasonably be swapped with no semantic difference (e.g. for a classification network, $\vec{y}_1 \cong \vec{y}_2 \iff \arg \max(\vec{y}_1) = \arg \max(\vec{y}_2)$). The local robustness safety predicate is then:

$$S(\vec{y}) = \begin{cases} \text{SAFE} & \vec{y} \cong NN(\vec{s}) \\ \text{UNSAFE} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2 (True Safety Probability). A function $P : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ returning the *probability* that the safety predicate S will return *SAFE* for a random point in \mathbf{R} .

$$P(\mathbf{R}) = \mathbb{P}(S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{SAFE} \mid \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R})$$

$P(\mathbf{R})$ represents the actual proportion of points in \mathbf{R} that satisfy the safety predicate. It serves as the ground truth against which verification engines are evaluated in Section IV.

Definition 3 (Adversarial Example). A point $\vec{x} \in \mathbf{R}$ such that $S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{UNSAFE}$, witnessing that \mathbf{R} is at least partially unsafe. Such a point is also called a **witness point**.

Definition 4 (Safe and Unsafe Regions). A region \mathbf{R} is **fully safe** if all points satisfy the safety predicate ($P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$), and **fully unsafe** if no points do ($P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$). While the traditional definition of unsafety includes any region that is not fully safe (i.e. $P(\mathbf{R}) < 1$), this paper distinguishes between fully safe regions and **partially unsafe** regions — those containing at least one unsafe point but not proven entirely unsafe.

We use the standard definitions of **soundness** (all proven statements are true) and **completeness** (all true statements are provable). As discussed in Section IV, these properties apply independently to each engine in VERAPAK — verification, falsification, and partitioning — and the framework’s overall soundness follows from their composition.

Definition 5 (Anytime Algorithm). An algorithm that (1) can be suspended and resumed with negligible overhead, (2) can be terminated at any time and returns some answer, and (3) produces results whose quality improves gradually with computation time [21], [22]

VERAPAK satisfies all three criteria, allowing it to be interrupted at any point and still return sound partial results.

Definition 6 (Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [1]). FGSM generates an adversarial input from $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ by perturbing it in the direction of the gradient of the cost function J with respect to the input:

$$\vec{x}_{adv} = \vec{x} + \vec{\epsilon} \odot [\text{sign}(\nabla_{\vec{x}} J(\theta, \vec{x}, \vec{y}))]$$

Here, θ denotes the network’s internal parameters and \vec{y} is the *ground-truth label* for \vec{x} (distinct from $NN(\vec{x})$). Because all generated adversarial inputs follow the same gradient direction, FGSM’s counterexamples tend to cluster along a single line in the input space.

IV. FRAMEWORK DESCRIPTION

The Refinement Cycle

VERAPAK’s operation is made up of three primary steps:

Verification: Apply a verification engine to determine if a region is provably safe, provably unsafe, or uncertain. Regions classified as `ALL_SAFE` or `ALL_UNSAFE` are terminal; uncertain regions proceed to partitioning.

Partitioning: Subdivide uncertain regions into smaller subregions where verification may succeed.

Falsification: Heuristically search each subregion for concrete counterexamples. Finding even one unsafe point upgrades a region from `UNKNOWN` to `SOME_UNSAFE`.

This cycle repeats until all regions are classified or a timeout occurs. Critically, VERAPAK exhibits *anytime behavior*: it can be interrupted at any point and return sound partial results indicating which regions have been definitively classified and which remain uncertain.

Key Innovations

VERAPAK has a number of defining characteristics that distinguish it from most tools in the verification space:

a) 1. *Covering Counterexamples:* Most verification tools use falsification only to quickly disprove safety. VERAPAK instead uses falsification to generate a *covering set* of counterexamples. Counterexamples are sought at every level of partitioning, creating a diverse set of counterexamples valuable for retraining, rather than clustered examples along a single gradient direction (FGSM) or just halting with a single witness point (most verification tools).

b) 2. *Iterative Completeness:* VERAPAK’s process of iterative refinement allows for verification engines with high levels of approximation to be used effectively. If these over-approximations create too much uncertainty, then VERAPAK will try again on a smaller region. However, we still get the benefit of their speed when these approximations are not too much. On all problems where the verification engine would succeed on its own, VERAPAK will succeed on the first try. Where it would fail, VERAPAK’s innovations can step in to provide a definitive answer where there previously was none.

c) 3. *Modularity:* Because these engines can be swapped out, the benefits of VERAPAK can be applied to any verification or falsification tool: past, present, or future. This grants VERAPAK some form of endurance against, and, in fact, adaptability to, the continuous advancement of research in this field.

d) 4. *Region Mapping:* VERAPAK can be used to map the decision boundary within a region if it crosses through. While this is not a novel idea on its own, it is a current field of study in neural networks [CITE]. Study on the utility of this is left to future works, though it is a notable side effect and may prove useful in the future.

Soundness and Completeness

VERAPAK maintains a clear separation between soundness and completeness:

Soundness (non-negotiable): All engines must satisfy soundness properties. Verification engines must never falsely claim a region is safe/unsafe (Properties ①–② below) or give false counterexamples (③ below), falsification engines must verify all claimed counterexamples, and partitioning engines must preserve all points (Property ① below). This ensures VERAPAK never makes false claims, even when interrupted early.

Completeness (best-effort): Engines may be incomplete. Verification may return `UNKNOWN`, falsification may fail to find existing counterexamples, and partitioning may not align with activation pattern boundaries. However, VERAPAK’s iterative refinement progressively reduces incompleteness: as regions shrink through partitioning, verification becomes more precise, and falsification has better chances of finding counterexamples. Practically, the framework will be terminated before it can eliminate incompleteness entirely, but it systematically minimizes it while maintaining soundness.

Region Classification and Data Flow

Throughout execution, VERAPAK maintains regions in three sets/queues representing different states of knowledge:

UNKNOWN: A queue containing non-terminal regions. Regions within may be in one of two states:

UNKNOWN state: Regions with no information. May be entirely safe, entirely unsafe, or mixed.

SOME_UNSAFE state: Regions with at least one verified counterexample (stored in `WITNESSES`). Known to be at least partially unsafe but not proven entirely unsafe.

ALL_SAFE: Regions proven entirely safe. Terminal; no further processing.

ALL_UNSAFE: Regions proven entirely unsafe. Terminal; no further processing.

WITNESSES: Points that are verified counterexamples. Often linked to a region in the `SOME_UNSAFE` state.

The main loop processes regions from the `UNKNOWN` queue until it is empty (complete classification) or a timeout occurs (partial results). The initial region(s) is placed in `UNKNOWN` with an `UNKNOWN` state. `UNKNOWN` is a queue so that information is handled in a breadth-first manner. If multiple regions are supplied, they will be processed at approximately equal depth at any time. Because these sets represent the state of the framework, the program can be paused or resumed by saving and loading this state. Since no data dependency exists between distinct regions, they can be checked in parallel. So

long as addition to and removal from the UNKNOWN queue is atomic, the observed speedup is linear with respect to the number of threads.

A. Verification

The verification step serves as the primary classification mechanism within VERAPAK, determining whether a given region can be conclusively labeled as entirely safe, entirely unsafe, or requiring further analysis. When a region r is pulled from the Unknown queue during the main loop, the $\text{Verify}(\mathbf{R})$ function routes it through the Verification Engine, which attempts to provide formal guarantees about the behavior of the neural network across all points within that region.

The Verification Engine returns one of several possible classifications. If the engine can prove that all points in the region satisfy the safety predicate, the region is immediately ALL_SAFE; if the engine can prove that *no* points in the region satisfy the safety predicate, the region is ALL_UNSAFE. However, when the Verification Engine cannot make such guarantees—either because the region contains or may contain both safe and unsafe points (returning either SOME_UNSAFE or UNKNOWN) or because the region exceeds the engine’s memory capacity (returning TOO_BIG)—VERAPAK moves on to the partitioning and falsification steps.

The interplay between verification and falsification allows VERAPAK to balance thoroughness with efficiency, progressively refining its understanding of the network’s behavior through iterative subdivision, and the choice of Verification Engine fundamentally shapes this process. Different engines offer varying levels of soundness, completeness, and computational efficiency, as detailed in the following subsections. VERAPAK’s modular architecture allows users to select verification strategies appropriate to their specific use case, whether prioritizing speed, precision, or memory efficiency.

IV-A.1. Definition: Verification Engine

A **verification engine** is a function $\rho_{safe} : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that, given a region, outputs a confidence value $\rho_{safe} \in [0, 1]$ representing the engine’s estimate of the region’s safety. The value ρ_{safe} should be interpreted as a confidence bound rather than the true probability $P(\mathbf{R})$.

a) *Required Properties (Soundness)*: All verification engines must satisfy the following soundness properties:

- ① $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0 \implies \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{UNSAFE}$
If the engine returns 0, the region is provably all unsafe.
- ② $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1 \implies \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{SAFE}$
If the engine returns 1, the region is provably all safe.
- ③ $x^* \neq \emptyset \implies S(NN(x^*)) = \text{UNSAFE}$
If the engine returns an adversarial example, it is provably unsafe.

b) *Optional Properties (Completeness)*: A verification engine may additionally satisfy the following completeness properties:

- ④ $P(\mathbf{R}) = 0 \implies \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0$
If the region is all unsafe, a complete engine detects it.
- ⑤ $P(\mathbf{R}) = 1 \implies \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1$
If the region is all safe, a complete engine detects it.

We denote a verification engine satisfying properties ①–⑤ as **complete**, and one satisfying only ①–③ as **sound but incomplete**. Most existing neural network verification tools, including ERAN, are sound but incomplete.

c) *Interpretation and Region Classification*: The value ρ_{safe} returned by a verification engine provides the following information:

- When $\rho_{safe} = 0$: We have a **proof** that the region is entirely unsafe ($P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$)
- When $\rho_{safe} = 1$: We have a **proof** that the region is entirely safe ($P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$)
- When $0 < \rho_{safe} < 1$: The engine is **uncertain**
 - For complete engines: The region definitively contains both safe and unsafe points ($0 < P(\mathbf{R}) < 1$)
 - For incomplete engines: The region may be entirely safe, entirely unsafe, or mixed; the engine cannot determine which

Remark 1. A value $\rho_{safe} = 0.8$ does *not* necessarily mean that 80% of the region is safe. Depending on the engine’s approximation method, this region could be 20% safe, 90% safe, or (for incomplete engines satisfying neither ④ nor ⑤) even 100% safe. The value ρ_{safe} represents the engine’s confidence, not the ground truth $P(\mathbf{R})$.

Based on the verification engine’s output and completeness properties, VERAPAK classifies regions as follows:

$$\text{verify}(\mathbf{R}) = \begin{cases} \text{ALL_UNSAFE} & \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0 & \textcircled{1} \\ \text{ALL_SAFE} & \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1 & \textcircled{2} \\ \text{SOME_UNSAFE} & x^* \neq \emptyset & \textcircled{3} \\ \text{SOME_UNSAFE} & 0 < \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) < 1 & \textcircled{4} \\ & \text{and complete} & \textcircled{5} \\ \text{UNKNOWN} & 0 < \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) < 1 & \textcircled{4} \\ & \text{and incomplete} & \textcircled{5} \end{cases}$$

Regions classified as ALL_SAFE are added to the Safe set; ALL_UNSAFE regions are added to the Unsafe set; SOME_UNSAFE regions are returned to the queue; and UNKNOWN regions undergo subdivision and falsification.

d) *Implementation Considerations*: In practice, verification engines may encounter regions that exceed available computational resources (memory or time). When a verification engine cannot process a region due to resource constraints, VERAPAK classifies this as TOO_BIG. TOO_BIG regions are processed identically to UNKNOWN regions: both undergo subdivision and falsification in the same manner. The TOO_BIG label serves primarily as a diagnostic indicator for understanding why a region could not be verified, but does not trigger any special handling in the main loop.

IV-A.2. Implementation: Discrete Search

Discrete Search is a complete verification engine applicable only to regions containing a finite number of discrete points. Rather than approximating the network’s behavior over the region, Discrete Search exhaustively evaluates the neural network at every point in the region and computes the exact proportion of safe points.

a) *Method*: For a discrete region \mathbf{R} containing points $\{\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_k\}$, Discrete Search computes:

$$\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k S(NN(\vec{x}_j))$$

This yields the exact value $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = P(\mathbf{R})$, where $P(\mathbf{R})$ is the true safety probability defined earlier.

b) *Completeness*: Because Discrete Search computes the exact proportion of safe points (and verifies any counterexamples it returns), it satisfies all five properties ①–⑤, making it a complete verification engine. The proofs of these properties are elementary when $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = P(\mathbf{R})$.

c) *Complexity*: Let $k = \prod_{j=1}^n |i_j|$ be the total number of discrete points in the region, where $|i_j|$ denotes the cardinality of interval i_j . Let $O(NN)$ denote the complexity of evaluating the neural network at a single point. Then Discrete Search has complexity:

$$O(k \cdot NN)$$

For continuous regions (where $k = \infty$) or regions with very large numbers of discrete points, this becomes computationally intractable, making Discrete Search practical only for small discrete regions or as a baseline for comparison.

IV-A.3. Implementation: ERAN (Modified)

ERAN (ETH Robustness Analyzer for Neural Networks) is an abstract interpretation-based verification tool that provides sound but incomplete verification. ERAN computes an over-approximation of the possible outputs for a given input region, then determines what proportion of this approximated output space satisfies the safety predicate.

a) *Abstract Interpretation*: ERAN uses abstract interpretation to compute a bounding box (or more complex abstract domain) that is guaranteed to contain all possible outputs of the neural network for inputs in \mathbf{R} . Let $ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R})$ denote this abstract output domain. ERAN guarantees soundness:

$$\forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : NN(\vec{x}) \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R})$$

However, ERAN is generally incomplete because the abstract domain may contain outputs that are not actually reachable by any input in \mathbf{R} :

$$\exists \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) : \vec{y} \notin \{NN(\vec{x}) \mid \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R}\}$$

This over-approximation occurs primarily when activation functions (ReLU, sigmoid, etc.) operate in their non-linear regions, requiring ERAN to approximate their behavior conservatively.

b) *Computing ρ_{safe}* : VERAPAK’s modified version of ERAN computes $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R})$ as the proportion of the abstract output domain that satisfies the safety predicate:

$$\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = \mathbb{P}(S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE} \mid \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}))$$

This is not the true safety probability $P(\mathbf{R})$, but rather a confidence bound based on the approximated output space. Critically, the percentage of the output space that is safe is not necessarily proportional to the percentage of the input space that is safe. A small input region can map to a large, diverse set of outputs (e.g., near decision boundaries), while a large input region can map to a concentrated set of outputs (e.g., in flat regions of the function). As such, ERAN’s value of $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R})$ does not map to the true probability $P(\mathbf{R})$.

c) *Soundness but Not Completeness*: ERAN satisfies the required soundness properties ①–③ but does not satisfy the optional completeness properties ④–⑤.

Property ①: $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0 \implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0 &\implies \mathbb{P}(S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE} \mid \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R})) = 0 \\ &\implies \forall \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) : S(\vec{y}) \neq \text{SAFE} \\ &\quad \text{Given: } S(\vec{y}) \in \{\text{UNSAFE}, \text{SAFE}\} \\ &\implies \forall \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) : S(\vec{y}) = \text{UNSAFE} \\ &\quad \text{Given: } \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : NN(\vec{x}) \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) \\ &\implies \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{UNSAFE} \\ &\implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 0 \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Property ②: $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1 \implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1 &\implies \mathbb{P}(S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE} \mid \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R})) = 1 \\ &\implies \forall \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) : S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE} \\ &\quad \text{Given: } \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : NN(\vec{x}) \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) \\ &\implies \forall \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R} : S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{SAFE} \\ &\implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 1 \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Property ③: $x^* \neq \emptyset \implies S(NN(x^*)) = \text{UNSAFE}$. x^* is always \emptyset . \square

Property ④ fails: $P(\mathbf{R}) = 0 \not\Rightarrow \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0$. Consider a region where all actual outputs are unsafe: $P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$.

Because ERAN’s over-approximation can include spurious outputs, there may exist a spurious safe output even when all reachable outputs are unsafe:

$$\exists \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R}) : \vec{y} \notin \{NN(\vec{x}) \mid \vec{x} \in \mathbf{R}\}$$

If we choose this spurious output to satisfy the safety predicate ($S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE}$), then:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(S(\vec{y}) = \text{SAFE} \mid \vec{y} \in ERAN(NN, \mathbf{R})) &> 0 \\ \implies \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) &> 0 \end{aligned}$$

This contradicts $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0$, demonstrating that ERAN can fail to detect all-unsafe regions. \square

Property ⑤ fails: $P(\mathbf{R}) = 1 \not\Rightarrow \rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1$. The proof is symmetric to Property ④. Even when all actual outputs are safe ($P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$), spurious outputs in the over-approximation may be unsafe, causing $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) < 1$. \square

d) Improving ERAN’s Completeness: In its standard form, ERAN can only return ALL_SAFE or UNKNOWN classifications. This limitation poses a significant challenge for VERAPAK’s iterative refinement strategy: if an all-unsafe region is repeatedly classified as UNKNOWN or SOME_UNSAFE, subdivision will continue indefinitely without ever terminating that branch of the search. This can be solved in one of two ways:

Method 1: Predicate Inversion. Run ERAN twice: once with the original safety predicate and once with the inverted predicate $\neg S(\vec{y})$. If the inverted run returns $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1$ (meaning all outputs satisfy the negated safety condition), we can definitively classify the region as ALL_UNSAFE. This approach doubles verification time in the worst case but can detect some all-unsafe regions that vanilla ERAN would miss.

Method 2: Extracting Abstract Domain Confidence. Modify ERAN to expose its internal abstract output domain representation, allowing direct computation of what proportion of the approximated output space satisfies the safety predicate. This yields $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) \in [0, 1]$ as described earlier. However, because this value includes over-approximations, any intermediate value $0 < \rho_{safe} < 1$ must be conservatively classified as UNKNOWN. VERAPAK uses this second approach.

Both methods, combined with VERAPAK’s falsification and partitioning strategies, allow the framework to achieve greater practical completeness than ERAN in isolation, even though the underlying verification engine remains theoretically incomplete.

e) Time Complexity: ERAN’s abstract interpretation has time complexity $O(L \cdot N_{max}^2)$, where L is the number of layers in the neural network and N_{max} is the maximum number of neurons in any layer [23]. The modified version used by VERAPAK adds negligible overhead for computing ρ_{safe} from the abstract domain, maintaining the same asymptotic complexity.

f) Space Complexity: ERAN’s memory usage is $O(N_{max}^2)$ for storing the abstract domain representations at each layer, because each node may contain a constant amount of information for each node in the previous layer. Only a maximum of two layers will be in memory at any one time. For very large networks or input regions, this can exceed available memory, resulting in a TOO_BIG classification that triggers subdivision.

While Discrete Search has better space complexity $O(N_{max})$ (only storing one evaluation at a time), its time complexity $O(k \cdot N)$ grows exponentially with input dimensionality ($k = \prod_{j=1}^n |i_j|$), making it impractical except for very small discrete regions. ERAN’s polynomial complexity makes it suitable for continuous regions and high-dimensional inputs where Discrete Search would be infeasible.

B. Falsification

The falsification step allows VERAPAK to terminate early, as well as to provide counterexamples for retraining. If any

counterexample is found, the region is deemed unsafe from a verification perspective, with a witness point for easy proof, and most verification tools stop here. However, VERAPAK also aims to create a strong set of counterexamples for retraining. As such, the existence of counterexamples makes the region SOME_UNSAFE: we’re not sure whether the region is *entirely* unsafe, but we know it is at least partially so. $\exists x^* \in \mathbf{R} : S(NN(x^*)) = \text{UNSAFE} \implies P(\mathbf{R}) < 1$. These generated counterexamples for a *covering* set: a set of adversarial examples distributed approximately uniformly across all unsafe subregions of the input space, rather than concentrated along a single gradient direction.

The core of this step is the Falsification Engine, which returns some number of points, and if any are unsafe, the region is marked SOME_UNSAFE with a witness (which is also saved to WITNESSES). If all of these points are safe, we gain no further knowledge besides that the region is partially safe, and so return it to the queue. This Falsification Engine can be any popular method of finding or creating counterexamples in a region.

One popular method of finding a counterexample is the Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [1]. FGSM takes the gradient of the loss function with respect to the input at a point and following that vector as a line in order to maximize the loss. However, because the counterexamples are all along a single line, the results have reduced utility for retraining. Retraining using FGSM increases robustness along that exact vector, but often does not improve safety along any other dimension.

We improve upon FGSM (Equation 1) through Randomized FGSM (RFGSM, equation 2), which combines gradient-guided search with controlled randomization. RFGSM computes the gradient as in FGSM, but then randomizes the input along the m dimensions where the gradient magnitude is smallest (i.e., directions where the network’s output is least sensitive to changes), while following the gradient in the remaining high-sensitivity dimensions.

$$\text{FGSM: } x_{adv} = \vec{x} + \vec{\epsilon} \odot [\text{sign}(\nabla_x J(\theta, \vec{x}, y))] \quad (1)$$

$$\text{RFGSM: } x_{adv} = \vec{x} + \vec{\epsilon} \odot [\text{sign}(\nabla_x J(\theta, \vec{x}, y)) \odot M + R \odot (1 - M)] \quad (2)$$

Here, M represents a vector mask of all but the m dimensions with the smallest gradient magnitude; R represents a random number.

When $m = 8$ dimensions are randomized in this way, the generated counterexamples span an 8-dimensional hyperplane in the input space (see Figure 1 for a visual comparison). This produces better coverage than FGSM’s single line, though as m approaches the full input dimensionality n , the computational cost per true counterexample increases dramatically (see Section V).

VERAPAK uses a diverse set of starting points, increasing the dimensionality further. Because the gradient is different across the input space, using a different starting point will yield a different hyperplane. Even when the computed gradient is similar, because the hyperplanes intersect the starting point,

Fig. 1: Counterexamples (red) from FGSM form a line. RFGSM extends this line along n dimensions (the vertical dimension in this figure).

the hyperplane will cover a different set of points. VERAPAK achieves this by running the falsification step after every partition, with a different starting point each time. These counterexamples will be distributed approximately evenly across the whole unsafe area of the region.

On a small enough resolution with a smooth gradient, the hyperplanes may indeed line up with one another, but the improvement of partitioning remains the same: spreading counterexamples across the entire input region.

IV-B.1. Definition: Falsification Engine

A **falsification engine** is a function $F : (NN : (\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m), \mathcal{R}) \rightarrow \{\vec{x} | \vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$ that generates a (possibly empty) set of candidate points within a region for safety evaluation. These points should be likely to falsify. Unlike verification engines, which attempt to prove properties about all points in a region, falsification engines search heuristically for concrete counterexamples.

a) *Required Properties:* All falsification engines must satisfy:

- ① $F(NN, \mathbf{R}) \subseteq \mathbf{R}$

All generated points must lie within the region being analyzed

This ensures that any counterexamples found are valid witnesses for the region's unsafety.

b) *Disabling Falsification: The Null Falsification Engine*, defined as $F(NN, \mathbf{R}) = \emptyset$ for all inputs, generates no candidate points. This effectively disables falsification, causing all regions to return to the UNKNOWN set after falsification.

c) *Soundness and Completeness:* Soundness and completeness in falsification mean something fundamentally different

than in the verification context:

Soundness: Falsification is sound if every point it claims is unsafe is actually unsafe. All falsification engines in VERAPAK are explicitly checked with $S(NN(\vec{x}))$, and no approximation occurs. Because all resultant points are indeed unsafe, **all falsification engines in VERAPAK are sound.**

Completeness: A falsification engine would be complete if, for any region containing at least one unsafe point, it always finds at least one such point (i.e. $P(\mathbf{R}) < 1 \implies |F(NN, \mathbf{R}) \cap \{\vec{x} : S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{UNSAFE}\}| > 0$). However, **no practical falsification engine is complete.** Falsification is inherently heuristic: it samples points hoping to find counterexamples but cannot guarantee finding them even when they exist. If such a guarantee could be made, it would be better described as a verification engine, telling us information about all points. Falsification provides concrete witnesses quickly when lucky or when the region is highly unsafe, whereas verification provides formal guarantees. Empirical results (Section V) show that falsification is particularly effective when $P(\mathbf{R}) < \text{SOME_NUMBER}$, finding counterexamples in most cases.

d) *Classification:* Based on the falsification engine's output, regions are classified as:

$$= \begin{cases} (\text{SOME_UNSAFE}, \vec{x}) & \exists \vec{x} \in F(NN, \mathbf{R}) : \\ & S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{UNSAFE} \\ \text{UNKNOWN} & \forall \vec{x} \in F(NN, \mathbf{R}) : \\ & S(NN(\vec{x})) = \text{SAFE} \end{cases}$$

When $F(NN, \mathbf{R}) = \emptyset$ (including the Null Engine), the second case applies vacuously, and the region returns to UNKNOWN. The UNKNOWN classification does not mean the region is safe, only that falsification failed to find counterexamples. Verification is required for definitive classification.

IV-B.2. Time Complexity

The complexity of $\text{Falsify}(r)$ using $F(NN, \mathbf{R})$ is dependent upon what Falsification Engine is used. Evaluation time $O(pN)$ (the time to evaluate the neural network on p points) should be added to each engine to get the time complexity of $\text{Falsify}(r)$. When $p = 0$, time and space complexity are always equivalent to the Null Engine.

Null: $O(1)$. No points are generated nor checked. (Note that $p := 0 \implies O(pN) = O(1)$)

FGSM: $O(N + p)$. One forward pass to evaluate the output, and one backwards pass to evaluate the gradient with respect to the input. Then p steps along that gradient.

RFGSM: $O(N + pm)$. Same as FGSM, except the p steps also include generating an m -dimensional random number.

Random Point: $O(pn)$. Computes p n -dimensional random numbers.

Center Point: $O(pn)$. Finds the p n -dimensional center points.

IV-B.3. Space Complexity

The minimum possible space complexity is $O(pn)$ in order to store the p n -dimensional points.

Null: $O(1)$. No points ever enter memory. (Note that $p := 0 \implies O(pn) = O(1)$)

FGSM: $O(P + pn)$, where P is the total number of parameters (weights and biases) that must be loaded for backpropagation, and pn is the storage for generated points. The memory used for evaluation is negligible compared to P .

RFGSM: $O(P + pn)$, the same as FGSM. Storage of random numbers is negligible and will always be less than or equal to the size of n .

Random Point: $O(pn)$. The memory used for generating random numbers is n , negligible compared to $O(pn)$.

Center Point: $O(pn)$. The memory used for calculating center points is $O(n)$, negligible compared to $O(pn)$.

C. Partitioning

Partitioning is the central innovation of VERAPAK, enabling iterative refinement that increases practical completeness of incomplete verification engines while generating spatially distributed counterexamples for retraining.

Partitioning is triggered in three circumstances:

Unknown Regions: When verification returns UNKNOWN, partitioning creates smaller regions where approximation error is reduced and the likelihood of the region containing both safe and unsafe points is reduced.

Resource-Constrained Regions: When verification returns TOO_BIG, partitioning reduces the computational burden by creating smaller subregions that fit within resource constraints. For abstract-interpretation verifiers like ERAN, smaller regions are less likely to span multiple activation patterns, reducing approximation error and computation cost for the subregion.

Partially Unsafe Regions: When falsification identifies a witness x^* in the region (giving the SOME_UNSAFE classification), partitioning separates the subregion containing x^* from potentially safe subregions, enabling more precise classification. Because the verification engine by definition gave UNKNOWN, the subregion zoomed in on x^* should contain less of the possibly safe space, hopefully giving us a more precise ALL_UNSAFE classification. This zooming operation occurs only after all Unknown Regions have been handled since we do have *some* idea of the contents of this region, whereas we have no idea about any of the Unknown regions.

Iterative refinement allows incomplete verifiers which would classically say “unsafe” whenever the region is partially unsafe, or might be so, to actually determine what *parts* of the region are actually safe versus unsafe.

By subdividing the input space, partitioning can generate a covering set of counterexamples that are distributed approximately uniformly across all unsafe subregions. This provides

a much broader overview of the network’s vulnerabilities compared to methods that only report the first failure found or create highly similar counterexamples. Further, any regions or subregions that are deemed safe by the verifier are terminal, and no computation is wasted trying to find counterexamples within these subregions.

IV-C.1. Definition: Partitioning Engine

A **partitioning engine** is a function $\Pi : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow [\mathcal{R}]^k$ that subdivides an input region into k non-overlapping subregions.

a) *Required Properties:* All partitioning engines must satisfy:

- ① $\bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{R}$
Coverage: Subregions cover the original region
- ② $\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathbf{R}_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$
Non-overlapping: Subregions are disjoint (or have measure-zero overlap)
- ③ Each $\mathbf{R}_i \subsetneq \mathbf{R}$
Strict Subset: Each subregion is a proper subset of the original region, strictly smaller than the original

b) *Optional Properties:* Partitioning engines may additionally satisfy:

- ④ $\text{Volume}(\mathbf{R}_i) \approx \text{Volume}(\mathbf{R})/k$ for all i
Balance: Subregions have approximately equal volume

Property ① (Coverage) implies witness preservation: for any point $x^* \in \mathbf{R}$, Property ① guarantees $\exists i : x^* \in \mathbf{R}_i$. Thus, known counterexamples are never lost during partitioning.

The number of partitions k is configurable at runtime by changing implementation-specific parameters.

IV-C.2. Implementation: Largest-First

The Largest-First strategy partitions along the dimensions with the greatest range, prioritizing dimensions where the region is most spread out.

a) *Method:* For a region $\mathbf{R} = (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n)$ where each $i_j = [l_j, u_j]$ is an interval:

- 1) Compute range for each dimension: $r_j = u_j - l_j$
- 2) Identify d dimensions with largest ranges
- 3) Divide each selected dimension into s equal subintervals
- 4) Create $k = s^d$ subregions that each map to a value in the Cartesian product of the lists of subintervals

b) *Rationale:* Partitioning large dimensions first:

- Reduces region volume most effectively
- Distributes counterexamples more uniformly
- Requires no gradient computation (fast)

IV-C.3. Implementation: Gradient-Based

The Gradient-Based strategy uses the network’s gradient to identify dimensions most sensitive to changes, partitioning along directions where the network’s output varies most rapidly.

a) *Method:* For a region \mathbf{R} with center point $c = \text{center}(\mathbf{R})$:

- 1) Compute gradient $\nabla_c NN(c)$ via backpropagation

- 2) Compute gradient magnitude for each dimension: $g_j = |\nabla_c NN(c)_j|$
- 3) Identify d dimensions with largest gradient magnitudes
- 4) Divide selected dimensions into s equal subintervals
- 5) Create $k = s^d$ subregions

b) *Rationale*: Partitioning along high-gradient dimensions:

- Approximates activation pattern boundaries (where gradients are large)
- Focuses refinement where network output changes most
- Can reduce approximation error faster than Largest First

c) *Trade-offs*: Gradient-Based is significantly more expensive than Largest First but may require fewer partition iterations to achieve classification. It is most effective for:

- Smaller networks where gradient computation is cheap
- Regions containing decision boundaries
- When verification cost significantly exceeds partitioning cost

IV-C.4. Termination Guarantees

A critical question for any iterative refinement framework is: Does partitioning ever stop?

a) *Floating-Point Limits*: In finite-precision computation, regions cannot be subdivided infinitely. Eventually, each interval $i_j = [l_j, u_j]$ in region $\mathbf{R} = (i_1, \dots, i_n)$ reaches floating-point resolution limits where l_j and u_j are consecutive representable numbers.

b) *Termination Conditions*: VERAPAK employs two termination strategies when regions become very small:

Discrete Search Fallback: When each dimension contains at most τ distinct floating-point values, switch to Discrete Search verification. This exhaustively evaluates all points in the region, providing exact classification. The result given may change slightly from machine to machine due to different numeric precision or representation, or optimizations that reorder or change operations that involve floating-point rounding. VNNCOMP2025 also seems to have independently discovered this issue in evaluation [24].

Boundary Classification: If verification engines are still classifying this region as UNKNOWN at the limits of floating-point precision, it is likely fundamentally undecidable: such regions likely either contain or are very close to the network’s decision boundary. As such, we give them the special classification of BOUNDARY regions.

c) *Theoretical Guarantee*: Let V_0 be the volume of the initial region and V_{min} be the minimum representable volume (determined by floating-point precision). After partitioning all regions in the queue into k equal subregions (assuming Property ④), the maximum volume of any region reduces by factor $\frac{1}{k}$. Thus, after t iterations:

$$V_t = \frac{V_0}{k^t}$$

Floating-point limits are reached when $V_t \leq V_{min}$, which occurs at:

$$t \leq \log_{\frac{1}{k}} \left(\frac{V_{min}}{V_0} \right)$$

Since this is finite, VERAPAK always terminates in finite time.

D. Soundness and Completeness

VERAPAK’s soundness depends on whether all outputs are provably correct, regardless of when the program is terminated. This depends on three claims: that all points in regions placed in ALL_SAFE and ALL_UNSAFE are provably safe and provably unsafe (respectively), that all points in WITNESSES are provably unsafe, and that this is the case no matter when or if the program is terminated. This section will prove these claims.

Completeness: VERAPAK terminates only when the result is complete. However, practically, the program will likely be terminated before such a result is obtained.

Verification Engine

Property ① Provably unsafe: $\rho_{safe} = 0 \implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$

Property ② Provably safe: $\rho_{safe} = 1 \implies P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$

Property ③ Witness validity: $x^* \neq \emptyset \implies S(NN(x^*)) = \text{UNSAFE}$

Falsification Engine

Property ① Contained: $F(NN, \mathbf{R}) \subseteq \mathbf{R}$

Partitioning Engine

Property ① Coverage: $\bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{R}$

Property ② Non-overlapping: $\mathbf{R}_i \cap \mathbf{R}_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$

Property ③ Strict Subset: Each $\mathbf{R}_i \subsetneq \mathbf{R}$

IV-D.1. Classification Soundness

Theorem 1. For any region \mathbf{R} classified by VERAPAK:

- If $\mathbf{R} \in \text{ALL_SAFE}$, then $P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$
- If $\mathbf{R} \in \text{ALL_UNSAFE}$, then $P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$
- $\mathbf{R} \subseteq I$ (initial region)

Proof. Regions are only added to these sets in the verification step:

- If verification returns $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 1$, then by Property ②, $P(\mathbf{R}) = 1$, and this is the only case where a region is added to ALL_SAFE.
- If verification returns $\rho_{safe}(\mathbf{R}) = 0$, then by Property ①, $P(\mathbf{R}) = 0$, and this is the only case where a region is added to ALL_UNSAFE.
- All other regions remain in UNKNOWN. □

IV-D.2. Witness Validity

Theorem 2. For any witness $x^* \in \text{WITNESSES}$:

- $x^* \in I$ (initial region)

- $S(NN(x^*)) = UNSAFE$

Proof. Falsification engines guarantee $x^* \in F(NN, \mathbf{R}) \subseteq \mathbf{R}$ (Property ①), and all regions are a subset of the initial region I . Therefore, $x^* \in WITNESSES \implies x^* \in F(NN, \mathbf{R}) \implies x^* \in I$.

The points given by the Falsification Engine are evaluated, and only added to the list of witnesses if $S(NN(x^*)) = UNSAFE$. The points given by the Verification Engine are known to be verified by Property ③. Therefore, $x^* \in WITNESSES \implies S(NN(x^*)) = UNSAFE$. \square

IV-D.3. Anytime Correctness

Theorem 3. VERAPAK can be interrupted at any point and all returned classifications remain sound.

Proof. Regions are moved to terminal sets (ALL_SAFE, ALL_UNSAFE) only after sound classification. Witnesses are placed in WITNESSES only after sound classification. Even if the program is forcefully terminated, none of these output sets will have any unevaluated outputs. \square

V. RESULTS

Results pending.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Future Work

- Hardware acceleration / GPU support
- Multi-threading
- Support for additional verification engines
- Additional classifications: KNOWN_MIXED (two witnesses), SOME_SAFE (with witness)
- Non-boolean classification for better mapping: ALL_SAFE/ALL_UNSAFE \implies ALL_CLASS0, ALL_CLASS1, ALL_CLASS2, etc.

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